

Succession Management and Organizational Survival in Selected Transportation Companies in Onitsha, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Inefficiency in succession management; lack of planning, poor staff mentoring and incompetent employees are major problems faced by transportation companies in Onitsha. The broad objective examined the relationship between succession management and organizational survival in some selected transportations companies in Onitsha. One research question and one hypothesis in line with the specific objective were employed. It employed descriptive research design, primary and secondary source of data are the major instrument used for the study. Descriptive statistical tool was used to analyze the data. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed to test the hypothesis. The findings revealed that mentoring has positive relationship with business continuity. Based on the finding, it is paramount for mentoring to be encouraged in the organization because it gives opportunities to develop competent, capable and productive employees who will enhance organizations growth even after the incapacitation or demise of the key stakeholder

INTRODUCTION

Effective succession management provides long-term sustainability, guarantees the survival of business and ensures capable and trained officials are in the organization. Many of the world's renowned organizations with the most longevity have their success rooted in effective succession management; these great companies begin planning their exit strategies right at the start of their appointment (Ohuabunwa 2015). Employees are bound to leave the organization through departures or retirement therefore; organization needs candidates who are qualified for key roles when positions become vacant. Not only does an organization lose skills when an employee departs, but it also loses valuable organizational knowledge. Succession management not only helps to ensure that there are candidates willing and able to step into the role of a departing employee, but also support strategies for knowledge transfer before a departure occur. (Flynn 2014)

Despite the benefits of succession management, many transport companies neglect planning for succession, they lack the skills to effect a smooth transition of leaders leading to the collapse of the organization soon after the demise or exit of the key players. Business failure in the transportation sector was due to the inability of organization planning for a successor (Sikinson 2012). They fear losing control to their subordinate and believe that the product of all their hard work can be in ruin without their presence because of this transition is marred with bottlenecks. Proper planning helps to avoid many glitches associated with succession and transfer of ownership (Eru 2013). Many of the transport organization operating today cannot name a successor. Ward (2000) added that succession management can be especially complicated because of the emotions involved and most people are not comfortable discussing topics such as aging, death and their financial affairs. They have poor attitude to retirement and do not deem it necessary to start mentoring those that will be in charge of their organization in their absence. It is hardly complicated and only becomes issues when the current occupant retires, forced out or suddenly dies, incompetent person may take over the organization, which he may be unable to run efficiently because he is not properly trained for the business. This could eventually end in prolonged crises that could undermine the survival of business. Succession Management requires continuous investment of time; resources and support by company's stakeholders, yet many avoid starting planning their exit or succession on time. They always bask in confidence that they still have many years of healthy life ahead (Ogundele, Idris & Ogundipe 2015). They do not have time to mentor and focus on the next generation of leaders and without a well-planned succession strategy, it is risky setting the firm up for chaotic period of transition, which could have a major negative influence in the organization.

Obadan & Ohioyenoye, (2013) opines that doing nothing about succession management is quite disastrous for organizations. Many transport organizations view it as an expense, rather than investment. Without adequate successor in place, the next generation of leadership and management of firms cannot maintain its character, let alone surviving. According to Dauda, (2013) most of the world admired states and corporations have achieved longevity because their Chief Executives Officers (CEO) starts planning their departure right at the beginning of their appointment. This seems to make sense because all the CEOs will ultimately come and go, and how that is being done has a profound effect on their corporations, which may largely determine the difference between extended periods of failure and success. In Nigerian organizations, the CEOs have hard times facing and accepting the impending loss of power, which is a necessary step for their succession plan. Some even find delegation difficult as it exposes some deals that need to be covered. As a result, the transitions are not as smooth as they should be. Succession management provides continuity of leadership, which is essential for companies to survive as CEOs and Senior Management positions become vacant due to retirement, as it allows organizations to place the right people in the right leadership positions for the future (Rothwell, 2005). Successful management transitions are generally the result of a major planning exercise that begins many years before Succession takes place.

In today's highly competitive global environment, human capital is an organizations most important asset, often differentiating highly successful businesses from those that struggle. Yet in the on going effort to develop a strong and capable workforce, many organizations focus almost entirely on hiring. They neglect succession management perhaps, the most essential ingredient in building an organization that is capable of achieving its strategic goals (Kevin & Tarry 2002). Succession planning serve as a way to create an organizational hierarchy, but it can also help organizations conduct an inventory of human capital and better understand gaps. Many organizations strive to identify key objectives and business goals and shape a work force accordingly. Although executives and senior managers play a crucial role in defining such organizations, there is a need for specific skills and competencies throughout the enterprise .The unexpected loss of key talents or the failure to fill critical roles in a timely manner cans quickly derail organizational goals. Combine such situations with a growing skills shortage, aging workforce and growing competition for high performers and it becomes obvious why organization must invest more time and more resources in succession management (Seniwoliba 2015)

Furthermore, many transport organizations are currently facing pressures to ensure their sustainability from the challenges of developing and retaining competent employees due to competition from other employers as the baby boomer generation begins to retire there are few young people in the workforce to replace them. Any organization that neglects mentoring the young employees would suffer skill gaps and non-availability of skilled employees that can sustain the organization (Ogunyomi 2013). A key indicator to measure organization stakeholders' capability is whether the organization can produce a viable heir apparent (Charan & Colvin, 1999).

It is noticeable that despite the changes and developments in the business environment, some firms still consider succession management as a time wasting exercise on the premise that the future is uncertain and would in any case, take care of itself.

Many firms do not have adequate succession plans that can cope with the large number of aging and retiring founders or executives (Rubin, & Illia, 2007 in Ofobruku & Nwakoby 2015). These few examples depict how the business world is also confronted with succession issues. Yet, it is known that the success of an organization is connected to the adequacy of its leadership progression that stems from succession strategies such as talent identification and internal leadership development (Sobol, Harkins, & Conley, 2007).

Notwithstanding the serious challenges that transport firms face, there are numerous examples of companies that have found the keys to longevity and prospered over the generations, creating wealth and sustaining employment in their Communities. Consistency in the leadership through effective succession management gives assurance of organizational survival. A leader who does not understand the strategies in place before the assumption of office may make decisions that will disorganize an already working strategy. Succession

management will benefit the employees, make an organization a more competitive employer, improve retention and engagement, and help to preserve valuable organizational knowledge. The aforementioned facts and the neglect by organizations to consider the influence of management's attitude to succession approach have made this research very imperative. To achieve outstanding results using succession management, an organization must develop an effective and highly focused strategy that centers on organizational excellence.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Succession management is a looming problem faced by transport companies in Nigeria. As their organizations grow, they are confronted with problem of continuity. Lot of these organizations are unable to achieve their objectives due to inefficiency in succession management; lack of planning, poor staff mentoring and incompetent employees who will succeed them after the retirement, resignation, death, incapacitation or termination of key players. These may lead to instability, discontinuity and eventual closed down of business.

Many business owners are yet to view succession management as a key contributor to the stability and continuity of their organization. They have very poor attitude to retirement, neglecting the need to mentor employees who will continue the business in their absent. These have led to the liquidation of many well-known Transport companies in Nigeria such as Emenika Motors and Be Kind Motors.

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to examine the extent of relationship between succession management and organizational survival in the selected transportation firms in Onitsha, Anambra state.

The specific objective is to determine the extent of relationship between mentoring and business continuity in selected transportation firms in Onitsha, Anambra state .

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between mentoring and business continuity in the selected transportation firms in Onitsha, Anambra state.

Hypothesis

H₁ : There is a positive relationship between mentoring and business Continuity

Significance of the study

The essence of this study is that most transportation firms in Onitsha are yet to view succession management as a key to the stability and continuity of their organization and that has jeopardize the survival of their business. The ability of the organization to manage their succession properly makes them a more competitive employer, improve retention and help to preserve valuable organizational knowledge. Future researchers will also benefit from the study.

Scope of the study

The study is focused on Succession Management and Organizational Survival in selected Transportation Companies in Onitsha. The research work selected four transport companies in Onitsha. Chisco Transport Company, Izuchukwu Transport Company, G U Okeke and ABC Transport limited..

11 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

. CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

SUCCESSION MANAGEMENT

Berke, (2005) entails Succession management as a comprehensive approach for identifying and developing a talent pool that enables an organization to have a list of adequately prepared candidates for filling all leadership

positions in an organization. It is a process, which involves the planning, selection and preparation of the next generation of managers, transition in management responsibility, gradual decrease in the role of previous managers and final discontinuation of any input by the previous manager (Erven 2007). It is more than filling the top spots, a smart management strategy that can drive retention of talent throughout the organization and make sure that the organization has the skills it needs in place, or on hand, to respond to the rapidly shifting sands that make up today's business environment (Hills 2009). In this sense, succession management provides organizations with systematic processes for; identifying developing and promoting the growth of high potential employees in the organizations succession pipeline (Leibman, Bruer and Maki, 2006).

Couch (2013). posits succession management as a deliberate and systematic effort to identify leadership requirements, identify pools of high-potential candidates at all levels, accelerate the development of mission-critical leadership competencies in the candidates through intentional development, select leaders from the candidate pools for pivotal roles and then, regularly measure progress. Rothwell (2005) posits that an effective succession management effort is that which is capable of building talent from within and ensures leadership continuity in key positions are retain , developing intellectual and knowledge capital for the future. it also encourage individual advancement which is design to ensure the continued effective performance of an organization, division, department, or workgroup by making provision for the development, replacement, and strategic application of key people over time. He contends that it is imperative for organizations to establish formalized succession planning as part of organizational strategic and management tools and suggests that systemic succession management can be attain by following his seven-pointed star model that consists of the following steps:

- Making commitment towards succession planning and management,
- Assessing present work and people requirements,
- Appraising individual performance,
- Assessing future work and people requirements,
- Assessing future individual potential,
- Closing the development gap, and
- Evaluating the subsequent succession development program.

Succession Management is about taking predetermine steps to make sure that business continuous moving when the founder or generations of managers should exit the business (Onyima, 2011). It involves the transition of managerial decision making in a firm from one generation to another so to ensure successful continuation of the business. Debapriya (2009) pointed out that succession management is not only there to ensure that the business continues after the death or retirement of the founder but it is there to make the organization continue to be competitive in its industry. Grzegorek (2009) believed that a successful management succession does not only require the transfer of ownership and control, but also requires the changes in the existing business model to facilitate competing performance. .

Ward (2000) defined succession management as the process of preparing to hand over control of the business to others in a way that is least disruptive to the business operation and values. it shows that the succession management as an on-going process and this means it should take a long time, he encourages at least five years before retirement. Which shows that succession management aims at transferring information and knowledge from the founder to the successor of the business as the founder grooms the successor on how to run the business as it results in the continuation of the business after the death or retirement of the founder. Succession management is a process of deciding how and when the management, ownership and control of the business will be transferred to subsequent owners (Sikomwe, et al 2012)

It ensures the identification, development, and long-term retention of talented individual (Schoonover, 2011).

Achumba (1989) defines Management succession as the process by which an organization replaces its staff so that continuity and profitability are not impaired, the process identifies employees who have the potentials to assume key positions, prepare them for advancement, while retaining them to ensure a return on the organizations training investment. Succession management involves recruiting employees, developing their skills and abilities and preparing them for advancement, while retaining them to ensure a return on the organizations training investment. It is important for any prosperity-focused organization to ensure that managers are available at the appropriate places and at the appropriate time (Hamilton. 2006). Succession planning can be regarded as attempt to design a plan for suitable number of managers and employees with key skills such that they can be suitable successors at time of retirement , death , disease or promotion of other employees and even new positions which are created in the future plans of the organization (Sambrook, 2005)

Succession management is the key to business continuity and longevity (Collins & Porras 1994), the point further emphasized by Collins (2001) that the best companies groom talented employees for positions of leadership. Collins (2009) even went further to show that most fallen companies had outside chief executive officers and leaders who fail the process of succession planning set their companies on a path to decline. Failure to engage in succession planning early on causes organizations to make decisions based on informal judgments, which are often problematic with negative results in most cases.) .With the attrition rate for companies increasing, it has become an inevitable strategy to be considered by every organization. To mitigate risk and to enhance quality of life of an organization, succession management is highly necessary. Effort made by leadership of organizations to recruit, develop and retain individuals with a range of leadership competencies capable of implementing current and future organizational goals (Leibman et al., 2006)

Noe, , Houston, , Hollenbeck, , Gerhart, & Wright, (2000) define succession management as a process of identifying and preparing suitable high potential employees to replace key players within the organization as their terms expire regardless of the expansion or contraction of the total workforce in the organizations, the need for good managers is critical and continuous. They further stated that the availability of the right number, right kind of management staff at the right time and in the right positions is imperative.

ORGANIZATION SURVIVAL

Organization survival is successful organizations, which are capable of achieving their objectives and goals and maintain it over a long period of time (Nwosu 2014). The goal of organizational survival underpins all goals (Adewale 2011). Paying attention to this goal contributes to the satisfaction and execution of other organizational goals as Gross (1968) posits the concept of survival as an unwritten law of every organization. He suggests that every organization must regard survival as an absolute prerequisite for serving any interest whatsoever and those that does not have survival as a primary objective or goal should have re-think .The most objective way to measure survival in organizations is to observe their continuing existence (Sheppard 2016). Survival of the organization in a vibrant and competitive business environment depends on how effectively the organizations learn to adapt itself to the environment and capitalize on its resources fully both human and material (Lee 2006 in Akani 2015).

MENTORING

Mentoring is a process whereby an experienced, highly regarded, empathic person (mentor) guides another individual (the mentee) in the development and examination of his or her own ideas, learning personal and professional development. Nnabuike & Nwogwugwu (2012) posit mentorship as a personal developmental relationship in which a more experienced or more knowledgeable person helps to guide a less experienced or less knowledgeable person. True mentoring is more than just answering occasional questions or providing ad hoc help. It is about an ongoing relationship of learning, dialogue and challenge .The mentor, who often, works

in the same organization or field as the mentee, achieves this by listening and talking in confidence to the mentee (Mentoringkit 2007). A mentor supervises, coaches and guides selected lower-level employees by introducing them to the right people and generally being their organizational sponsor (William & Greg 2002).

Business mentoring enables the positive transmission of organizational values, culture, goals and vision (Egwu 2012). He maintains that mentoring has positive implication for those being mentored, mentors and the organization. According to him, when people properly choose their mentee whom they are sure would be committed, loyal and patriotic leadership successor, they are happier that their efforts would not be in vain at the end. The mentor has a willingness to devote his energy to produce his successor while the mentee have a loyalty to act according to the dictates of the mentor, all to the benefit of the organization. Nwogwugwu (2012) states that adequate mentorship enables the mentored to aspire to the heights of their mentors to be like them, and even in some cases perform better than they do. In addition, mentoring increases the skills, abilities and talents of one being mentored (Hall and Smith 2009 in Egwu 2012) Mentoring involves direct relationship with the mentor and the mentored; there is face-to-face contact, which offers a fertilizing opportunity for the growth of trust and confidence in the parties. This allows the mentor and the mentored to give opportunities for the development of competence, capabilities, productivity and performance (Nwosu 2014).

Ugwu (2012) said that in organization where mentoring is well established, , the “RIPE CORN” or “CASH COWS” are isolated very clearly in their carriers and mentored into excellence. Successful organization, as a matter of policy, put measures in place to discover young people whom they think has what it takes to take their organization to the promise land. These classes of people though might be picked from management trainee level are mentored into excellence and allow grow through the ranks to take over the leadership of the organization in future time. This basic technique entails identifying in advance the specific subordinate best suited to serve as the next chief executive.

BUSINESS CONTINITY

A Management discipline that ensures an organization has in place the appropriate measures and plans to: reduce the like hood that an incident will prevent the organization from serving its customers, reduce the impact of business if incident occurs, recover from the incident and allow the organization to continue serving its customer whilst it recovers from the incident.(Ukagdon 2013) .The capability of an organization to continue delivery of its product or services at acceptable predefined levels. It identifies potential threats if realized, might cause, and which provide a framework for building organizational resilience with the capability of an effective response that safeguards the interests of its key stakeholders, brand, reputation and value creation activities (BCI 2012)

The development, implementation and maintenance of policies, strategies and programs to assist an entity manage a business disruption event, as well as build entity resilience. It focuses on ability to achieve organizational objective. The capability assists in preventing, preparing for, responding to, managing and recovering from impact of business disruption event. This includes natural disasters, pandemics, significant loss of utilities, financial crises, accident and incident that threaten organizational reputation (Watterston 2009)

. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on Relay Succession Planning theory by Santorin Joseph (2004). The theory states that current Chief Executive Officer(CEO) of an organization should pass the baton to a successor over a long period. The impact of companies practicing this theory is being evaluated in Santorin's research compared with organizations that do not have such plans in place. It was recorded that organizations that practice relay succession plans performed better because the successors were exposed to corporate challenges and were able to deal with such challenges in the pre-succession phase. Obviously, current CEO was able to pass the baton in real time and this would give the successor the opportunity to test the reins of leadership and at the time receive

training. In similar direction, organizations that implemented relay succession should perform better in the post-succession phase, because he has been tried and tested, which implies that his experience would speak for him.

The relevant of this theory to this study is for the predecessor to ensure that there is a successor in place. This is to enable the successor to become competent, and capable of running the business after the predecessor must have gone.

SUMMARY OF EMPIRICAL REVIEW

So many literature were reviewed, the effect of succession planning on the survival of Nigeria firms, management succession planning and corporate survival in Nigeria, Mentoring, Strategic Human Resource Management and Succession Planning in Nigeria, Succession Planning in Small Business Enterprises in Edo State of Nigeria, Business Mentoring and Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria and Role of Succession Planning on Survival of Small and Medium Family Enterprises after Retirement/Death of the First Generation Entrepreneurs in Kenya.

All these research dealt on aspect of succession planning, mentoring and survival, none emphasized on the importance of mentoring and business continuity in transportation companies thereby creating a gap, which this study tries to fill. This study closes the gap by analyzing the relationship between mentoring and business continuity in the selected transportation firms in Onitsha.

111 METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study employed descriptive research design whose purpose is to collect detailed and factual information that describes an existing phenomenon.

POPULATION OF STUDY

The population of the study comprises the staff of four selected transport firms in Onitsha. They are four transport companies in Onitsha. Chisco Transport Company, Izuchukwu Transport Company, G U Okeke transport company and ABC Transport limited. Due to the small number of the total population, the researcher decides to use complete enumeration method that is the entire participants.

Table 3.1 Schedule of the Population Size

Names of company	no
Chisco transport	8
Izuchukwu transport company	7
G U Okeke transport	10
ABC transport company	8
Population size	33

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Data for the research was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The respondents were placed on five points likert scale. The secondary data are information gathered from e-books, textbooks and journals.

VALIDITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

The study adopted content validity. The objective of the study runs in line with the hypothesis and research questions. The literature review carries enough content to close the gap identified. Experts from the field of management read the work and departmental format was used. The supervisor also read though and offered corrections, which were effected by the researcher.

RELIABILITY TEST:

The reliability of the items used in the research instrument was measured using Cronbach’s alpha test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.824	10

From the table above, the computed Cronbach/Coefficient Alpha value was .824 N = 10, which means that .824% of the variance in the scores is reliable variance. as suggested by most value greater than .70 indicates a degree of internal consistency.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical tool was used to analyze the data collected with the aid of questionnaire. The tools include tables and frequency tables. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed to test the hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.01 with the use of SPSS version 20.

Descriptive statistics table

SN	ITEMS ; Mentoring and business Continuity	N	Min mum	Maxi mum	Mean	STD. devi ation
1	One of the surest avenue of effecting succession management in the organization is through mentorship	30	3.00	5.00	4.5667	.67891
2	My organization has mentoring as an avenue for building subsequent future leaders	30	1.00	5.00	4.7333	.78492
3	Developing young employees with skills help the organization to avoid losing valuable and experience staff necessary for business continuity	30	3.00	5.00	45000	.68229
4	Mentoring is a positive foundation in global business continuity through assurance of effective leadership.	30	1.00	5.00	4.4333	.97143
5	Training programs helps my organization to remain focus towards its objectives and strategy	30	4.00	5.00	4.7000	.46609
6	Effective mentoring helps in transmitting the values goals culture and vision of organization to the employees	30	1.00	5.00	4.7667	.50401

7	The training programs and work situation of my organization is capable of keeping it from collapsing in times of crisis	30	2.00	5.00	4.1333	.62881
8	Effective training, coaching and monitoring ensures business's continuity	30	3.00	5.00	4.2333	.50401
9	The organizations considers mentoring as an unavoidable necessity for continuity	30	4.00	5.00	4.7000	.46609
10	The organization considers development of employees as unavoidable necessity for continuity unavoidable necessity for continuity	30	4.00	5.00	4.8000	.40684

CORRELATIONS

		MENTORING	BUSINESS CONTINITY
MENTORING	PEARSON CORRELATION	1	
	SUM OF SQUARES & CROSS PRODUCTS COVARIANCE	4.492 .155	.639** 2.864 .099
	SIG. (2 TAILED)		.000
	N	30	30
BUSINESS CONTINITY	PEARSON CORRELATION		1
	SUM OF SQUARES & CROSS PRODUCTS COVARIANCE	.639** 2.864	4.475 .154
	SIG. (2 TAILED)		.000
	N	30	30
** Correlation is significant at 0.1 level (2-tailed)			

Source: SPSS Version 20

Discussion of Findings

Based on the outcome of the analysis carried out, it was revealed that there is significance relationship between mentoring and business continuity in transportation companies. The positive impact of mentoring will make the organization sustainable for business continuity. When organizations ensure that employees are properly mentored, developed and trained to assume the position of a successor, it makes such organization continue in business in spite of the absence of the predecessor. The organization moves on knowing that there is a competent successor in place. This is in line with the work of Ogunyomi (2013) which says that adequate mentoring will drastically reduce the problem of succession of a key player and will enhance business growth.

Conclusion

The goal of every organization is continuity and effective succession management ensures the survival of the organization. Studies have shown that firms that strategically put in place a well articulated effective succession management policy would definitely encounter continuous existence. Therefore, it is paramount for organizations to encourage well-developed mentoring programs because it helps the management to avoid losing valuable and experience employees necessary for organizational continuity

4.4 Recommendations

Organizations should encourage well-developed mentoring programs because it helps the management to avoid losing valuable and experience employees necessary for organizational continuity.

Mentoring should be encourage in organization as unavoidable necessity for continuity because it gives them the opportunities for the development of competence, capable and productive employee's who will guide its growth even after the incapacitation or demise of the key stakeholder.

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